

Project title: All Data 4 Green Deal - An Integrated, FAIR Approach for the Common European Data Space

Project number: 101061001

Project Acronym: AD4GD

Type: HORIZON-AG - HORIZON Action Grant Budget-Based

Work program topics addressed: HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01

DELIVERABLE No: D7.3
GDDS EXPLOITATION PERSPECTIVES (INITIAL)

Due date of deliverable: 29/02/2024

Actual submission date: 29/02/2024

Version: 1.0

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DOCUMENT METADATA

Project number	101061001
Project title	All Data 4 Green Deal - An Integrated, FAIR Approach for the Common European Data Space

Deliverable title	GDDS exploitation perspectives (initial)
Deliverable number	D7.3
Deliverable version	1.0
Contractual date of delivery	29/02/2024
Actual date of delivery	29/02/2024
Document status	Final version
Document version	1.0
Online access	URL
Dissemination	Public
Work package	WP7
Partner responsible	Design Terminal (DT)
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Abstract	<p>The present deliverable provides exploitation perspectives of the AD4GD project after 18 months of work on designing and implementing building blocks to fulfil the needs of the project pilots. It describes the process in which aims to co-create and shape the European Green Deal Data Space as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of pollution, biodiversity, and climate change.</p> <p>The deliverable introduces the AD4GD exploitation methodology and outlines exploitation activities made by the submission of this deliverable and the results of the exploitation workshops and individual work fulfilled together with the project partners and with the stakeholders. Moreover, it presents the initial individual and joint exploitation perspectives identified during the first half of the project and a market analysis to understand different opportunities to scale up project results.</p> <p>The deliverable can identify 11 KERs that are considered the key components for the development of the rest of the project lifetime. During the second part of the project, these KERs will be analysed and prioritised and an exploitation and sustainability strategy will be developed</p>
Keywords	exploitation, KER, strategy
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DOCUMENT VERSION HISTORY

Version history			
Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
0.1	01/12/2023	Initial Table of Contents and document set up	Katalin Szilagyi
0.2	02/02/2024	Initial inputs	Katalin Szilagyi
0.3	26/02/2024	Partner comments Finalisation for last round of inputs	Dr Sébastien Ziegler Joan Masó Lucy Bastin Katalin Szilagyi Diego de la Vega
0.4	28/02/2024	Editorial inputs	Katalin Szilagyi Diego de la Vega
1.0	29/02/2024	Final version	Katalin Szilagyi

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AD4GD	All Data 4 Green Deal project
API	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
ATOS	Citizen Science
AU	Aston University
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CitSci	Citizen Science
CREAF	Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals
ECCP	European Centre for Certification and Privacy
ECMWF	European Centre For Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
D7.1	Deliverable D7.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation, including standardisation and communication activities
DT	Design Terminal
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
FIT	Fraunhofer -Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.
GD	Green Deal
GDSS	Green Deal Data Space
IoT	Internet of Things
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin

MI	Mandat International
ML	Machine Learning
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium Europe
PSNC	Instytut Chemii Bioorganicznej Polskiej Akademii Nauk
RDF	Resource Description Framework
STA	Sensor Things API
STaplus	Sensor Things API plus (extension of STA)
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable provides exploitation perspectives of the AD4GD project after 18 months of work on designing and implementing building blocks to fulfil the needs of the project pilots. It describes the process in which aims to co-create and shape the European Green Deal Data Space as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of pollution, biodiversity, and climate change.

The deliverable introduces the AD4GD exploitation methodology and outlines exploitation activities made by the submission of this deliverable and the results of the exploitation workshops and individual work fulfilled together with the project partners and with the stakeholders. Moreover, it presents the initial individual and joint exploitation perspectives identified during the first half of the project and a market analysis to understand different opportunities to scale up project results.

The deliverable can identify 11 KERs that are considered the key components for the development of the rest of the project lifetime. During the second part of the project, these KERs will be analysed and prioritised and an exploitation and sustainability strategy will be developed.

1 INTRODUCTION

D7.3 is a public document, part of *Work Package 7 on Standardization, Outreach, and Exploitation* within the context of *Task T7.4 Exploitation and sustainability plan*. For a complete overview, this document should be read together with deliverable *D7.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation, including standardisation and communication activities*. The first deliverable illustrated the initial dissemination and exploitation strategy planned to carry through the project.

This first iteration of the final exploitation deliverable is due in Month 18, February 2024, and is intended to be a living document continuously updated during the project's lifetime, serving as a reference for the AD4GD project partners. The exploitation timeline and methodology have been reviewed and adapted in alignment with the project's actual focus and outputs.

In Month 36, August 2025, the draft plan will be turned into an actionable final exploitation plan, including partners' own individual exploitation plans and the AD4GD joint exploitation plan, specifically Deliverable *D7.4 GDDS exploitation perspectives (final)*. This document will summarise the selected Key Exploitable Results (KERs), exploitation mechanisms, and stakeholders interested in sustaining and upscaling the outcomes of the project.

1.1 DELIVERABLE STRUCTURE

D7.3 is structured into 8 sections, as follows:

1. *Introduction*: This section introduces the context for the deliverable.
2. *AD4GD at a glance*: This part briefly introduces the AD4GD project and its pilots.
3. *Strategy for exploitation*: This section serves as a summary of the exploitation strategy, including updates compared to the initial plans detailed in D7.1. The methodology explains the different actions and tools used so far to produce the first findings of individual and joint exploitation perspectives. The strategy follows the plan, implement, validate structure to offer insights into the next steps of exploitation actions. The intention is to guide project partners in creating individual and joint exploitation plans, which can be continuously revised during the implementation of the project and culminate in a final actionable exploitation and business plan.

4. *Initial exploitation perspectives:* This section outlines the first steps in the exploitation route, the individual KER collection done with the partners individually and during the 1st workshop. It also presents the results of the 2nd workshop focusing on identifying joint KERs to work with them in the second half of the project. Moreover, it summarises the interviews with the partners regarding the joint exploitation plan and a draft version of the identified joint KERs.
5. *Market analysis from an exploitation angle:* The short study provides a review of the current European data market relevant to the AD4GD context. The review assesses the demand versus the value proposition and identifies competitive advantages with the assistance of the partners. The report initiates the AD4GD data stories case studies, intended to be published alongside the extended edition of the market analysis. Once the final project results are agreed upon by the consortium partners, further reviews can take place as part of the AD4GD business plan.
6. *Further project activities supporting the exploitation and sustainability:* This section lists opportunities provided by the European Commission and the collaboration done so far with other projects and also provides brief insight on the stakeholder management regarding the pilots and the activities organised with them.
7. *Next steps:* Upcoming actions of the plan, implement and validate methodology are explained under section 7. The explained activities are taking place the next 18 months of the project, as far as the project progresses based on its original milestones. The section reveals collaboration plans and activities with related projects and offers an insight to the next expected deliverable contents.
8. *Conclusions and references:* this section concludes the deliverable and list the references used.

2 AD4GD AT A GLANCE

AD4GD's mission is to co-create and shape the European Green Deal Data Space as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services that support the key priorities of pollution, biodiversity, and climate change. The focus is set on interoperability concepts that bridge the semantic and technology gaps which currently prevent stakeholders from multi-disciplinary and multi-scale access to data, and which impede the exploitation of processing services and platforms at different levels including Cloud, HPC and edge computing.

This project aims to enable the combination and integration of data from remote sensing, established Virtual Research Environments and Research Infrastructures, Internet of Things (IoT), socio-economic data, Citizen Science (CitSci) in an interoperable, scalable, and reliable manner. Integration will be facilitated by including semantic mappings and different standards and dominant models that bridge domain- and data source-specific semantic concepts such as the Essential Variables framework, as well as applying machine learning and geospatial user feedback to ensure quality, reliability and trustworthiness of data and transforming spatial scales.

AD4GD will demonstrate through multi-scale, multi-criteria, and multi-actor pilots the applicability and added value of data fusion for improved accessibility and decision making in the European Green Deal Data Space by focusing on the key priority areas of zero pollution, biodiversity, and climate change. Pilot cases will be designed to demonstrate the feasibility of reusing, developing, extending and integrating a range of tools, semantics and standards to facilitate data-driven decision making on Green Deal priority topics.

- **Water pollution:** Berlin's small lakes are ecological hotspots at risk due to various climate and urban stressors. In addition, they also suffer from a lack of information on their condition. In this pilot we are developing water quality and availability indicators to improve decision-making by integrating IoT sensor data with satellite and citizen science data.
- **Biodiversity:** The project will establish key locations for landscape functional connectivity and endangered species persistence by explicitly combining and cross validating the results from different accepted modelling approaches.
- **Air Quality:** the project will employ low-cost IoT sensors, focusing on PM10 and PM2.5, to enhance air pollution understanding and forecasting by involving communities in monitoring. The initiative seeks to provide detailed local air quality insights, supporting informed health decisions and establishing replicable models for urban air quality enhancement.

3 STRATEGY FOR EXPLOITATION

The AD4GD exploitation task helps ensure sustainability for the AD4GD project by identifying expected individual partner and project level results at an early stage. This will help to better position the program towards external stakeholders prior to the stakeholder validation workshops.

Exploitation focuses on making sure results reach stakeholders who can take them forward, making concrete use of them for several purposes. The main goal of AD4GD's exploitation plan (which was fully presented in the deliverable D7.1 in Month 6) is to analyse and discover the different sustainability paths of the project outcomes and translate them into a set of possible products and service offerings with associated features, quality of services and support.

The AD4GD exploitation plan step by step:

1. **Starting with the analysis of market potential:** A market overview is prepared for the project consortium based on the Results of the new European Data Market study 2021-2023. The objective is to understand different opportunities to scale up project results. Data story case studies will be initiated with the AD4GD pilots, in which the mapped stakeholders will be engaged at a later stage, to evaluate the usability of the developed project outcomes from an end user perspective.
2. **Building a methodology:** The exploitation methodology developed is built in a co-design manner and includes knowledge transfer elements on different sustainability pathways collected both from consortium partners and previous projects' results. The methodology developed includes amongst others, a market study literature review, internal and external interviews, and online and offline focus group co-creation workshops. Following the initial exploitation perspectives D7.3, strategic stakeholder meetings and a dedicated validation workshop is planned towards the second half of the project. Iterative exploitation plan (individual and joint) reviews are organically embedded in the exploitation plan.
3. **Continuing by collecting individual and collective sustainability plans:** Collecting key exploitable results (KER) and mapping key stakeholders through structured questionnaires and interviews with partners responsible for developing the results. Working more closely with the pilot actions will facilitate the organisation of the validation workshops with the exploitation target groups and translate them into tangible results.

4. **Finally, narrowing it down to the final exploitation action plan:** Summarising the selected KERs, exploitation mechanisms and stakeholders interested to sustain and upscale the outcomes of the project. The key outcome will become the main component of the AD4GD business plan.

As a result of the work on the different exploitation pillars, the following outcomes are equally expected as framed in the project proposal:

- Creation of an active and agile exploitation ecosystem
- Definition of an operational and deployment plan, ensuring that technologies and solutions developed by the project can be realised in real-life conditions.
- Definition of the value chain, players needed to put the data space in operation and cost-benefit analysis.

Figure 1: Development of exploitation action plan

The exploitation task is also related to the promotion of future sustainability and quality evaluation of the project. It includes activities such as announcing the results and achievements of the project, presenting the advantages of the services and support developed and identifying stakeholders willing to promote the results in the future. These activities are led by Mandat International within the tasks T7.1 Strategy for communication and dissemination and T7.2 Communication and dissemination activities.

3.1 METHODOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABILITY

The exploitation methodology developed was built in a co-design manner and includes knowledge transfer elements on different sustainability pathways collected both from consortium partners and previous projects' results. The methodology is developed including a literature review, internal and external interviews, online and offline focus group co-creation workshops, strategic meeting summaries towards the second half of the project and an iterative review organically embedded in the exploitation plan.

PLAN

- **Individual exploitation plan perspectives:** AD4GD project partners' exploitation plans submitted at the project proposal stage have been revisited at the project launch. The intention was to check the validity of the original exploitation plans and explain to partners the Exploitation methodology and plans.
- **Setting the basis: explaining the knowledge valorisation, exploitation, and dissemination:** The first partner level co-creation workshop took place in Leipzig, Month 11, 2023 July. Before the meeting, an online session was held to explain the workshop methodology. At the face-to-face meeting, all participants attended a recap session on the definition and key objectives of exploitation actions and the knowledge valorisation concept.

- **Validation and partner cross-check of individual plans:** During the co-creation session, the focus was on the individual exploitation plans, where partners reviewed each other's exploitation perspectives, to ensure clarity and cross-check replicability and potential to convert individual plans into joint actions. The workshop included some gamification components, where partners had voting rights. See results under section 4.1.
- **Towards a joint exploitation plan:** Following the thorough reviews of individual partner exploitation plans, in September 2023 an online co-creation workshop took place. With the help of a Miro funnel, the aim was to narrow down the replicable and joint exploitation plans towards a joint exploitation idea and identify the partner's contribution capacities. See results under section 4.2.
- **Focus group interviews and collection of contributions:** As a next step, at the end of 2023 individual interviews took place with the lead partners to identify the AD4GD top three KERs. These findings are currently being analysed on individual partner level and will be the candidates submitted to the Horizon Exploitation Booster Service.

Further parts of the methodology for sustainability are part of the next 18 months' activities and can be equally found under section 7. Next steps.

- **Horizon Exploitation Booster service:** A first consultation took place with the Horizon Results Booster management team to identify opportunities and learn about the application and submission process. It is planned to submit the AD4GD application in early 2024.
- **Follow up on individual exploitation perspectives:** Following the first outcomes of the Horizon Results Booster exploitation services, partners will revisit the individual exploitation perspective and facilitate the final review process of their own business plans. This will be supported through online consultation, a questionnaire, and a final exploitation plan template.

IMPLEMENT

- **Data Story case studies:** AD4GD intends to compose three short pilot case studies from the exploitation angle. These case studies will be reported in the final exploitation deliverable, in the *D7.4 GDDS exploitation perspectives (final)*.
- **Joint exploitation Business plan:** As a follow-up of the initial market study, the final deliverable will include the AD4GD KER's business plan.

VALIDATE

- **Stakeholder validation workshop:** An additional co-creation workshop will be hosted, where mapped stakeholders will be invited to validate either the joint KER or the pilot level individual exploitation plans based on mutual agreement between the AD4GD consortium.
- **Green Deal Data Space cross-disciplinary exploitation workshop:** Given the strong correlation between the Data Spaces Green Deal projects: GREAT¹, B-Cubed², FAIRiCUBE³ and USAGE⁴, it is

¹ <https://www.egi.eu/project/great-project/>

suggested to host an online cross-disciplinary exploitation webinar after the project midterm review.

4 INITIAL EXPLOITATION PERSPECTIVES

Based on the exploitation plan set in deliverable D7.1, the following activities were taken, and results were reached regarding partner and project level exploitation.

4.1 INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION PLAN PERSPECTIVES

Individual exploitation ideas were collected online at the beginning of the project, focusing on the main sustainability objectives. Each partner identified how they are planning to benefit from AD4GD results in the future individually. This collection was presented in the deliverable D7.1 in Month 6, 2023 February, and serves as a basis, during the project implementation, partners update and revise them continuously during the project progress to have their final exploitation plan by the end of the project.

The individual collection was followed by an offline exploitation workshop during the 2nd project meeting in Leipzig in Month 11, 2023 July. During this collaborative activity, partners got familiar with each other's exploitation plans and cleared out uncertainties. Moreover, they checked cross-fertilization and replicability possibilities.

The following individual exploitations plans were identified by the partners:

<p>1. Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals- CREAM:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standards implemented in MiraMon GIS and RS software and its MiraMon Map browser including quality tools. Essential Variables vocabularies included in the GeM+ (Metadata editor). QualityML enrichment.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STAplus client tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tapis: Tables from APIs for Sensors (Sensor Things API plus Explorer) connected to the MiraMon Map Browser supporting extended JSON schema (semantic tagging). ○ Further development of the MiraMon GIS and RS software by including Extended JSON schema (semantic tagging) configured using the GeM+ and STAplus support. ○ GeM+ enriched with Essential Variables vocabularies and QualityML enrichment. ○ Meaning service to store extended JSON Schemas that define the attributes of data (based on NiMMbus). ○ Connectivity maps methodologies (with AU and ATOS)
<p>2. Open Geospatial Consortium Europe- OGC:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rainbow (Definition Server) implementation of Green Deal Data Space vocabularies for Essential Variables.

² <https://b-cubed.eu/>

³ <https://fairicube.nilu.no/>

⁴ <https://www.ogc.org/initiatives/usage/>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OGC academy: Best practice for semantically describing variables (with CREAM).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> White paper 'OGC standards for data spaces' (with CREAM and in collaboration with other projects).
3. ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL- ATOS:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atos will integrate the results generated in the AD4GD project and specifically in the WP5 Work Package to improve the capabilities of its AI and HPC products' portfolio (ThinkAI). HPC is the use of supercomputers and clusters to solve advanced computation issues with a huge amount of resources. The results will be integrated into the AI platform (new models, knowledge, etc.). OGC academy: Best practice for semantically describing variables (with CREAM).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green Platform: A platform which offers green services to the EU stakeholders, integrating more type/ sort of sensors to analyse and solve more issues. Moreover, to create specialised AI models to sell the processed information to corporations and to provide AI based services to reduce unnecessary information.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the implementation of the GDDS in the "IDSA style" there is a need for a GDDS facilitator that will deploy the necessary services (Certification services, authentication services, logging services, etc.). This set of services could eventually become the "final" GDDS and need sustainability.
4. Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin- KWB:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prioritisation of measures concerning the water quality and availability for small lakes in Berlin and improvement of the transferability of solutions for the urban water cycle by using standardised data and data processing.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Surface water emission tool: Further develop a tool that describes critical pollutant loads from urban surfaces into lakes. The tool already exists for small rivers.
5. Instytut Chemii Bioorganicznej Polskiej Akademii Nauk- PSNC:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PSNC will use the experience and insights from the work to enable semantic interoperability in the GD data space, to cross-fertilize and contribute to other data space related projects where PSNC participates, e.g., AgriDataSpace, Datamite, ILIAD, etc. Related to this, PSNC will also use the experiences and results from the design and implementation of the AD4GD information, as input (and showcase) to the standardisation process of the Agriculture Information Model (AIM), which is being leveraged in AG4GD and other related projects like ILIAD. The results related to the tools for data integration will be used to extend PSNC Open-Source solution and promote its usage.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Agriculture Information Model (AIM).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tools (Open-Source solutions) for data integration.
6. Fraunhofer -Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung e.V.- FIT:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fraunhofer FIT will use the collected insights from the multi-actor analysis (WP1) to cross

<p>fertilise and to contribute to other ongoing data space projects at Fraunhofer like the "Datenraum Kultur". The idea of the multi-actor approach (MAA) is to make sure that projects really tackle actual problems that regular users have, in our case for example researchers, decision makers, data owners and publishers and so on. By fixing real problems and getting the end-users involved during the development, the final product ends up being something that people use. MAA also tries to involve different perspectives from the actors (also known as stakeholders). To achieve this, we will conduct different methods like interviews or group discussions with the stakeholders (mostly qualitative methods).</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strengthen Fraunhofer's standpoint with the planned activities with citizen scientists (WP2) regarding citizen participation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scientific publications in international journals and conferences to support doctoral students in their PhD studies.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use experiences from the prototypes of the pilot studies in our competence centre and EDIH-European Digital Innovation Hub (Transfer projects) to bring hands-on experience to manufacturing SMEs on how to deploy and use data spaces.
<p>7. European Centre For Medium-Range Weather Forecasts- ECMWF:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ECMWF is responsible for implementing Pilot 3; enable technical integration new sources of data to key existing Earth Observation and Earth-Observation-based data platforms;
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop a sandbox environment for testing applications and workflows; evaluate performance aspects.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incentives: ECMWF can find a way to incentivize data providers (private, CitSci, public...) to adopt standards for their APIs and datasets.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ECMWF will develop its internal systems to support novel observation sources such as IoT data. Where possible it will make this data FAIR and coherent with other tools and services being built by the project and the wider GDS project. Sandboxes are already available through services like the European Weather Cloud and Wekeo.eu. Sandbox in this context refers to a computing environment where testing and experiments can be done without impacting wider systems.
<p>8. European Centre for Certification and Privacy- ECCP:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ECCP will push an extension of its Europrivacy Certification Scheme on data spaces to the Europrivacy International Board of Experts. <p>The scheme assesses and certifies the compliance of data processing activities with the GDPR and complementary national data protection regulations. It enables applicants (e.g., companies) to identify and reduce their risks, to demonstrate their compliance with the data protection requirements and obligations, and to enhance their reputation and market access. In other words, a certification scheme is a set of rules and standards that companies can follow to show they handle the processing of personal data and privacy properly. If a company satisfies these standards and gets certified, the certification serves as a sort of official stamp of approval that a company is reliable and trustworthy when it comes to data processing activities.</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Have a website and community and network, a single space for future discussion.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Europrivacy might be proposing a new set of domain-specific criteria, checks and controls, and extension to the Europrivacy detailed list of criteria, checks and controls on the domain of earth observation data.
<p>9. Design Terminal- DT:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design Terminal will run a hackathon for its' startup alumni or for external startups (agritech, mobility and space industry related startups, especially who are focusing on satellite data) using the platform database. During the hackathon, several challenges were set, and teams should find solutions to these challenges while using and working with the dataset and database.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Design Terminal might create an AD4GD startup spinoff pathway plan.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exploitation workshop: The developed workshop method can be used in different projects with different partners in the future.
<p>10. IoT Lab:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● IoT Lab will use the development made in the AD4GD project, particularly WP3, to extend its IoT services to dataspace. As IoT Lab is also involved in other research and development communities such as FIWARE (FIWARE is providing different open-source software components) and TM Forum. IoT Lab can promote and exploit the AD4GD results with the open-source software provided by these communities. FIWARE: https://www.fiware.org ; TM Forum: https://www.tmforum.org/.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Standard representation of all Essential Variables in common format, in machine readable way, semantic vocabularies (in collaboration with CREAM, OGC, AU and PSNC).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● STApplus services for the GDDS: Harmonisation tools between FIWARE and STA. Through the utilisation and mapping of standardised data models will notably ensure the interoperability between FIWARE and STA.
<p>11. Mandat International- MI:</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● As a non-profit foundation, MI will exploit project results particularly through the pursuit of future research actions which intertwine the various data sources with vertical-specific datasets (e.g., health, social sciences). It will also exploit AD4GD results in the international standardisation communities, including ITU-T (International Telecommunications Union Standardization Sector (International Telecommunications Union Standardization Sector) and ISO.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create dataspace for specifications. Having a replicable specification of dataspace for different projects.
<p>12. Aston University- AU:</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AU will exploit experience and knowledge gathered through the project to strengthen its engagement with standardisation and industrial / policy outreach. We will generate evidence-based knowledge from the pilot studies which will lead to scientific publications in international journals and conferences. We will make use of project assets and deliverables in scale-up activities, follow-up projects and further applied research. Plans are to engage with standards working groups such as ISO 19157, PPSR_CORE, OGC OMS SWG and OGC APIs WGs, to align with relevant standards as they develop, be aware of any duplication of effort and network with potential users and applications domains for AD4GD deliverables.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Semantic uplift of air quality vocabularies to be used for citizen science projects.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open workflows for calculating landscape connectivity. Not commercially exploitable as all open source but adds value to existing open source for scientists.

Table 1: List of individual exploitation pathways

As mentioned, partners checked cross-fertilization and replicability possibilities as well regarding their identified exploitation pathways. They voted about their exploitation perspectives and whether they can be considered joint/ replicable exploitable results as well.

Individual exploitation plans have been analysed and looked at by each partner from the perspective of whether they can be transferred into joint exploitation results and if they are replicable. This expressed further potential to join forces between the partners and to better understand the commercialisation opportunities for those results which have the possibility for multiplication and scaling up.

The results of these votes were considered during the identification phase of the project level Key Exploitable Results (KERs).

From the above listed partner level KERs, the following were identified as joint or replicable:

Individual exploitation perspectives	Partner's votes	
	Joint	Replicable
Cross-fertilize and contribute to other data space related projects using the result on AD4GD interoperability.	12	7
Using AD4GD design and implementation, as inputs and showcases in standardisation processes.	12	7
Extend open-source solutions based on AD4GD results.	12	7
Strengthen engagement with standardisation and industrial / policy outreach, based on knowledge and experience gathered.	11	8
Scientific publications and conference participation, based on the generated knowledge from the pilot studies.	11	8
Using standards in the international standardisation communities, including ITU-T and ISO.	7	7
Future research actions which intertwine the various data sources with vertical-specific datasets	7	7
Run a hackathon for startups (who are using data, eg. satellite data) using the platform database. During the hackathon, several challenges were set and teams should find solutions to these challenges while using and working	6	7

with the dataset and database.		
Using standardised data and data processing to improve water quality.	6	1
Using standards implemented and Essential Variables vocabularies included in the AD4GD in other projects.	5	5
Technical integration of new sources of data to key existing data platforms.	5	2
Develop a sandbox environment for testing applications and workflows.	5	2
Rainbow (Definition Server) implementation of Green Deal Data Space vocabularies for Essential Variables.	4	7
Integrate the results generated to improve the capabilities of its AI and HPC products' portfolio (ThinkAI).	3	7
Extend IoT services (providing different open-source software components) to dataspace.	2	4

Table 2: Joint/ replicable perspectives in partners' individual exploitation plans

Figure 2: Snapshot from the co-creation workshop in Leipzig

4.2 TOWARDS A JOINT EXPLOITATION PLAN

The second co-design workshop with the partners was held in Month 13, September 2023 to discuss the suggested joint exploitation products/services listed above and to identify common attributes, and elements in them and group them, which could be in focus as possible exploitation perspective for the whole AD4GD project.

The following common elements were identified during the co-design workshop:

- Standardisation/ Integration strategy
- Datasets, data models, databases
- Cross-fertilization with other data spaces
- Semantic components
- User interface
- Platform, infrastructure
- Scientific and usage policies, measures
- Joint scientific publications
- Collaboration with other projects

Figure 3: Snapshot from the online co-creation workshop towards a Joint exploitation plan

4.3 THE AD4GD EXPLOITATION JOURNEY

After the cross-fertilization voting and the online workshop on identifying project level KERs, DT, as exploitation task leader conducted an interview with CREAM, AD4GD lead partner together with MI, WP7 leader in Month 15, November 2023 to decide on the 3 main project level KERs to work with during the second half of the project. This list was discussed with the project partners and extended during the 3rd project meeting in Turin, on Month 18, February 2024 and in line with the discussions on the components necessary to implement the pilots in AD4GD.

The list initially contained 6 main project level KERs but it was extended to 11, in a process that brings consistency with the deliverable *D6.1 Pilot Technical implementation planning, implementation and assessment*.

The list of KERs might be extended in the second part of the project lifetime with further possible exploitable elements. The KERs will be analysed and prioritised and an exploitation and sustainability strategy will be developed. This should be done in collaboration with the Green Deal Data Space Action Group in EuroGEO.

List of main KERs identified for AD4GD:

1. New datasets and databases:
<p>Datasets and databases are created in the concept of the pilot and will be used within the pilots. The three kinds of datasets are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water quality/quantity in lakes in Berlin; ● Habitat connectivity maps in Catalonia; ● Better air quality maps for Europe.
2. Standards / Common language:
<p>Several standards are being considered for the design and the implementation of the AD4GD solutions (OGC SensorThings API, etc.) The developments in AD4GD are inputs to the relevant Standard Developments Organizations who will improve the standards accordingly.</p>
3. Blueprint of future data space:
<p>The blueprint is a review of the Data Spaces Building Blocks based on previous literature, mapping to current solutions and needs for data spaces emerged during the AD4GD solutions developments.</p>
4. Components of the pilots to support semantic enrichment
<p>Components are tools for tagging data fields (e.g. columns in csv files or fields in Web Feature Services) with terms from agreed vocabularies. Could be used for discovery of data which represent the same phenomena.</p>
5. GD Information model and supporting tools
<p>It is an RDF system based on Virtuoso Open source to manage the GD information model and ingest data that can also be exposed as STA. It is also applied to the Agricultura Data Space and the ILIAD digital</p>

twin of the ocean.
6. TAPIS
A STA visualisation client and table visualisation done in pure Javascript mainly focused on observation data and semantic enrichment of tabular data
7. STA service based on FROST server
A deployment of FROST server with STApplus extension that contains some sensor data from the pilots and can become a node in the GDDS
8. RAINBOW service
A repository of concepts reusable in the GDDS that is maintained by OGC and applied to other Horizon Europe projects.
9. Automated Ingestion of Data from Diverse Low-cost Sensors
A set of ingestion tools of IoT and observational data into the STA FROST server.
10. Meaning catalogue
A storage service that contains descriptions of the data model and the semantic of observational data. It is based on a previous development to store Geospatial User Feedback called NiMMbus.
11. ML modelling and prediction facility
A cloud deployment of data and processing power and code to execute ML models. It contains executable trained ML models for lakes (tested initially in Berlin) and habitat connectivity maps based on land cover data from remote sensing.

Table 3: List of main KERs identified for AD4GD

This list is considered a living document, partners will work with the identified KERs by elaborating on the following aspects in the second half of the project:

- Relevant to implement the AD4GD pilots
- Potential users, and stakeholders who could use the KER;
- Value proposition/benefit for users;
- Encouraging target users to use the KER;
- Commercial potential, if any;
- Competitors, if any;
- Potential impact, contribution to potential impact;
- Partners' contribution to the KERs individually within the AD4GD project implementation.

5 MARKET ANALYSIS FROM AN EXPLOITATION ANGLE

A primary market overview is performed to understand opportunities and base exploitation and business plans on realistic market interest scenarios for the next half of the AD4GD project. Core assumptions are based on the Results of the new European Data Market study 2021-2023 and its Data Stories.⁵ Relevant sections of the referenced reports and case studies have been collected and compiled into this section to serve as the preliminary market analysis. It is aimed to be informative and act as guidelines for the partners to estimate potential impact and commercialisation opportunities for their exploitation plans.

The market potential:

The European Data Market (EDM) study, overseen by the consortium IDC-Lisbon Council, has been actively tracking the progression of the European data economy since 2013. Offering valuable insights and empirical evidence, the EDM study sheds light on the diffusion of the data economy across various industries and regions. Its findings have significantly influenced the development of European policy strategies in this domain. From the initial indications of big data's potential disruptive effects, this ongoing monitoring and analysis have underscored the social and economic significance of data-driven innovation. Presently, the advent of artificial intelligence tools and services fuelled by data is expediting this transformative process, as evidenced by the analysis and scenarios presented in the latest reports of the previous edition of the study (SMART 2016/0063).⁶ Additionally, the European Data Market study⁷ ran between 2015 and 2020. It aimed to define, assess, and measure the European data economy, supporting the achievement of the Data Value Chain policy of the European Commission.

In the context of the AD4DG project, we looked at the referenced study, which also produced key facts & figures for the year 2025 according to three alternative evolution paths and of the European Data Market and Economy and driven by different macroeconomic and framework conditions. As explained in the report, the 2025 scenarios are shaped by a combination of economic and social drivers, focused on the interaction of two main axes:

- *the high or low pace of diffusion of data-driven innovation, driven by demand-supply dynamics, and its impact on economic growth.*
- *the social and economic data governance model enabling a fair and competitive economy, as indicated by the new European Data Strategy*

This analysis highlights the critical turning points to be faced in the next years by governments, businesses, and social actors in the development of the European Data Economy. The combination of alternative social and economic trends results in the following scenarios:

- *The **Baseline scenario** is characterised by a healthy growth of data innovation, a moderate concentration of power by dominant data owners with a data governance model protecting personal data rights, and an uneven but rather wide distribution of data innovation benefits in the society. This is considered the most likely scenario.*

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/results-new-european-data-market-study-2021-2023>

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/results-new-european-data-market-study-2021-2023>

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-data-market-study-2015-2020>

- *The **High Growth scenario** is characterised by a high level of data innovation, low data power concentration, an open and transparent data governance model with high data sharing, and a wide distribution of the benefits of data innovation in the society.*
- *The **Challenge scenario** is characterised by a low level of data innovation, a moderate level of data power concentration due to digital market fragmentation, and an uneven distribution of data innovation benefits in society.*

In terms of realistic scenarios, given the due date of the D7.3 deliverable being close to the target year of the updated European Data Market Study report, we can safely focus on the first two scenarios (Baseline and High Growth) when assessing the market potential for the AD4GD exploitation results:

*'In the **Baseline scenario**, the EU 27 GDP cumulative growth average in the period 2020-2025 (+1.5%) will sustain the investments in the digital economy and consumer willingness to spend. As a result, the Data Market is forecast to reach 82.5 billion euros in the EU27, with a compound annual growth rate of 5.8%. The Data Economy will grow faster than the Data Market, thanks to a positive multiplier impact of data innovation on the economy, reaching a value of 550 billion Euro in the EU27, with a steep increase of its incidence in the EU from 2.8% in 2020 to 4% in 2025.*

*In the **High Growth scenario** in 2025, the EU 27 GDP compound annual growth rate in the period 2020-2025 (+2.1%) will be 1.5 times higher than in the Challenge scenario and 40% higher than in the Baseline scenario. This will accelerate investments in the digital economy and consumer willingness to spend. In the European Union, public and private investments will accelerate in Artificial Intelligence, advanced robotics, automation as well as new skills. As a result, the Data Market is forecast to reach 107 billion euros in the EU27, with a compound annual growth rate of 11.5% between 2025 and 2020. The Data Economy will grow faster than the Data Market, reaching a value of 827 billion Euro in the EU27, with an incidence on EU GDP of 5.9%, against the 4.0% of the Baseline scenario.'*

In the context of the study, it is worthwhile mentioning the European Data Market Monitoring tool initiative: *'The European Data Market (EDM) monitoring tool aims to provide essential information to the European Commission on the size and trends of the EU data market and data economy, the number of data professionals, the number of data companies and the revenues created by them.'*

Such a tool provides the AD4GD consortium with valuable insights that can inform strategic decision-making, product development, marketing strategies, and resource allocation to maximise opportunities and mitigate risks within the market landscape.

Data4Green: Why Data-Driven Innovation is Key to Delivering the EU Green Deal⁸

Beyond the European data market potential, it is equally important to assess the relevance of the Green Deal-related data-sharing potentials and interests. The selected report referenced in the title shows that data analytics is present across all the priority areas of the European Green Deal with a wide range of impacts. It can help with mitigation, for instance by reducing carbon emissions through precision agriculture. And it can help with adaptation, for instance by better predicting floods.

The report used the format of so-called data stories, which inspired the initiation of data story case studies for the AD4GD project pilots.

⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/results-new-european-data-market-study-2021-2023>

The example data stories in the new European Data Market study consist of three main parts:

- *The opportunities of Data4Green with an overview of the relevant European policy context, an explanation of the green data value cycle, a taxonomy of data-driven applications for the green transition, a reflection on the expected impact of such applications and a look at several startups that are active in the described domains.*
- *Specific cases on the ground provide a more profound insight into the mechanisms through which data can impact the green transition.*
- *Policy implications derive from the analysis of the opportunities and challenges in the preceding sections.*

Report conclusions: *The contribution of data and digital technologies to the green transition does come at a cost for the environment itself. The information and communication industry's contribution to global greenhouse gas emissions was estimated to fall between 3.0 and 3.6% of total emissions in 2020, with the potential to exceed 14% of the 2016 net emissions in 2040.⁹ While recognizing this downside of the digital and green twin revolution, the scope of this data story is limited to the potential positive impact that data-driven innovation may have on tackling climate change.*

Startup landscape:

As predicted and explained in the above study, the European green data economy presents a fertile ground for startups that are committed to innovation, sustainability, and environmental stewardship. With increasing awareness of climate change and the growing importance of sustainability in business operations, the demand for green data solutions is expected to continue driving innovation and investment in the region.

Between 2021 and 2024, the European startup landscape within the green data economy has undergone a remarkable evolution. Fuelled by increasing environmental consciousness and regulatory pressures, startups in this sector have experienced exponential growth and innovation. In the wake of climate change concerns and the push for sustainability, a multitude of startups have emerged, specialising in renewable energy, energy-efficient technologies, carbon offsetting solutions, and data centre optimization. Moreover, advancements in artificial intelligence and IoT have played pivotal roles in optimising energy consumption and enhancing overall operational efficiency within data centres. The landscape has witnessed a surge in investment, with venture capitalists and governments alike recognizing the potential for scalable solutions that align profitability with environmental stewardship. This evolution signifies a profound shift towards a more sustainable and conscientious approach to data management and infrastructure in Europe, laying the groundwork for a greener digital future.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.12.239>.

Snapshot of startups using data for green outcomes in the European Union arranged by policy area from 2021:

Figure 4: Startups using data for green outcomes in the European Union arranged by policy area. Source: Dealroom's database of startups¹⁰

Fresh insight into currently active Climate Data companies and startups in 2024 can be found on the FS6 100 top Climate Data companies and startups in 2024 webpage.¹¹

Policy angle and further considerations:

The European Commission Digital Strategy¹² designed a new, confident role for Europe as a global player. Realising that the European model has proved to be an inspiration for many other partners worldwide, the strategy calls for the EU to strengthen its commitment towards setting global standards for emerging technologies and to remain the most open region for trade and investment in the world.

In terms of standards, in particular, the EU has paved the way for the setting of global standards for 5G and the IoT and is now committed to leading the standardisation process of a number of additional advanced and new-generation technologies such as blockchain, quantum computing, supercomputing – all technologies that lie behind and allow data sharing and data usage and that, as a straight consequence, are directly linked to the further development of a well-functioning Data Economy.

This proactive international role in the standardisation process is accompanied by a robust commitment to trade and investments on the international scene to ensure that a collaborative and inspiring European

¹⁰ <https://app.dealroom.co/companies.startups>

¹¹ <https://www.fs6.com/companies/climate-data/mo>

¹² https://commission.europa.eu/publications/european-commission-digital-strategy_en

approach on several technology-related topics -including data flows and the possibility to pool available and relevant high-quality data together - is successfully implemented.¹³

The European Commission has been very active and proactive in the forefront of strengthening its digital sovereignty and set standards with a clear focus on data, technology, and infrastructure. Its motto reflecting on the current policy priorities symbolises well its focus area: '*A Europe fit for the digital age*'.

Between the most recent European Commission policy acts and actions¹⁴, two specific regulations are brought to the attention of the AD4GD partnership indirectly impacting their exploitation plans:

The Data Act:

The Regulation on harmonised rules on fair access to and use of data – also known as the **Data Act** – entered into force on 11 January 2024¹⁵. The Act is a key pillar of the European data strategy¹⁶ and it will make a significant contribution to the Digital Decade's¹⁷ objective of advancing digital transformation.

The new measures complement the Data Governance Act¹⁸, which was the first deliverable under the European strategy for data and became applicable in September 2023. While the Data Governance Act regulates processes and structures that facilitate voluntary data sharing, the Data Act clarifies who can create value from data and under which conditions. Together, these two acts will facilitate reliable and secure access to data, fostering its use in key economic sectors and areas of public interest. They will also contribute to the establishment of an EU single market for data, ultimately benefiting both the European economy and society at large.

The Data Act will enable a fair distribution of the value of data by establishing clear and fair rules for accessing and using data within the European data economy, a necessity heightened by the growing prevalence of the Internet of Things (IoT)¹⁹. Thanks to this Regulation, connected products will have to be designed and manufactured in a way that empowers users (businesses or consumers) to easily and securely access, use and share the generated data.

The Data Act is a cross-sectoral piece of legislation (i.e. it lays out principles and guidelines that apply to all sectors). It does not modify existing data access obligations; however, any forthcoming legislation should align with its principles.²⁰

Environmental, Social, and Governance regulations:

The new European Commission ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) regulations represent a comprehensive framework aimed at promoting sustainable and responsible business practices across the European Union. These regulations encompass a range of requirements designed to integrate ESG factors into corporate decision-making processes, disclosure practices, and investment strategies.

¹³ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/results-new-european-data-market-study-2021-2023>

¹⁴ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age_en

¹⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/european-data-act-enters-force-putting-place-new-rules-fair-and-innovative-data-economy>

¹⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/strategy-data>

¹⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/europes-digital-decade>

¹⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-governance-act>

¹⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/internet-things-policy>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-act#:~:text=The%20Data%20Act%20is%20a,the%20protection%20of%20personal%20data.>

ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) regulations wield a profound impact on data-driven green startups, reshaping their operational landscape and strategic outlook. As regulatory frameworks increasingly emphasise sustainability and responsible business practices, startups must navigate stringent compliance requirements while leveraging data-driven approaches to address environmental concerns. ESG regulations compel these startups to integrate sustainability metrics into their data analytics models, fostering transparency and accountability in their operations. Moreover, compliance with ESG standards enhances their credibility among investors, unlocking access to capital and fostering long-term growth opportunities. However, startups face challenges in balancing regulatory compliance with innovation, as stringent guidelines may impose constraints on data collection and processing. Nonetheless, ESG regulations ultimately drive green startups to innovate responsibly, fostering a culture of sustainability and resilience in the evolving landscape of data-driven enterprises.

6 FURTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES SUPPORTING THE EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability and collaboration between projects and stakeholders are vital components in the modern landscape of innovation and development. Sustainability, often defined as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, has emerged as a guiding principle across various sectors.

Collaboration plays a crucial role in advancing sustainable initiatives. By pooling resources, expertise, and networks, collaboration can leverage collective strengths to address complex challenges more effectively.

6.1 OPPORTUNITIES PROVIDED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

To optimise the utilisation of its outcomes, AD4GD will consider using the exploitation opportunities provided by the European Commission. These include sharing results by the Communication lead on platforms at the end of the project, such as the Horizon Results Platform²¹, Innovation Radar²², Open Research Europe²³. Moreover, AD4GD will consider contacting the Horizon Results Booster²⁴ initiative to request supervising services regarding the existing communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies and future business plan development activities to reach additional improvements.

Beyond the consortium level exploitation findings, the first level joint exploitation plans will be submitted by 2024 May to the Horizon Result Booster program to fine tune the ideas and reveal their feasibility through training and guidance services in the 2nd half of 2024 as follows:

- review of the key exploitable results of the project;
- revise, complement and clarify existing exploitation plans of project results and/or outline exploitation paths of results;
- techniques to identify all relevant stakeholders in the exploitation value chain;
- support to perform a risk analysis related to the exploitation of results.

This extra service could supplement the existing exploitation progress of the project and could contribute to further improving the existing project strategies towards effective exploitation of key exploitable results.

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

²² <https://innovation-radar.ec.europa.eu/>

²³ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

6.2 THE GDDS ACTION GROUP

For better outreach and longevity, AD4GD is actively engaging with sister projects in their common goals towards the future European Green Deal Data Space. This collaboration is articulated by the Green Deal Data Space Action Group in EuroGEO²⁵ integrated by:

- Sister projects financed under the same Horizon call to develop the GDDS including AD4GD, FAIRiCUBE²⁶, USAGE²⁷ and B-Cubed²⁸.
- The GREAT project²⁹, delivers the initial blueprint of the Green Deal Data Space.

Other projects that contribute to or benefit the Green Deal Data Space such as OEMC project³⁰, EO4EU³¹, EIFFEL³² and ILIAD³³. Regular meetings are held monthly with the project coordinators of the mentioned projects to keep an update on the work carried out by each other and to detect possible common perspectives.

The outcomes of GREAT (DIGITAL CSA)³⁴ outcomes are definitive from the AD4GD pilots' perspective on how to establish data governance requirements, a technical architecture and priority datasets for the data space.

Similarly, to the AD4GD intentions, DS4SSCC³⁵ project (DIGITAL CSA) prepared a blueprint for the creation of a data space for smart communities. This toolkit will be inspirational to create the AD4GD pilot data strategy and to customise the data-based services.

Finally, Destination Earth (DestinE) flagship initiative³⁶ is planning to use the data spaces as new data sources (including the GDDS where AD4GD is contributing) as data sources of data lakes that can serve as data sources for the European Digital Twins. A potential opportunity for the AD4GD consortium is to discover the possibility to engage in the DS4SSCC-DEP (DIGITAL CSA) deployment action, to accelerate the rollout of local or thematic Digital Twins.

6.3 STAKEHOLDER MAPPING AND ENGAGEMENT

To successfully customise AD4GD outcomes, partners must first take into account which stakeholder groups can benefit from its results and why, as well as which groups can also help with the further exploitation of project outcomes. Thus, several stakeholders were identified regarding the AD4GD Pilots (water pollution, biodiversity, air quality) for future collaboration in the first round. Later on, further stakeholder groups will be created in connection with the joint exploitation perspectives of the project and further collaboration activities will follow.

During the AD4GD project kick-off meeting held in Month 1, September 2022 in Barcelona, Spain, a Preparatory Stakeholder Analysis workshop was held to identify and prioritise potential stakeholders and users of systems and services to be developed by the AD4GD project. The highest priority stakeholders

²⁵ <http://beyond-eocenter.eu/index.php/about-us/eurogeo-actions>

²⁶ <https://fairicube.nilu.no/>

²⁷ <https://www.usage-project.eu/>

²⁸ <https://b-cubed.eu/>

²⁹ <https://www.greatproject.eu/>

³⁰ <https://earthmonitor.org/>

³¹ <https://www.eo4eu.eu/>

³² <https://www.eiffel4climate.eu/>

³³ <https://ocean-twin.eu/>

³⁴ <https://www.egi.eu/project/great-project/>

³⁵ <https://www.ds4sscc.eu/>

³⁶ <https://destination-earth.eu/>

were interviewed, and the results were discussed and reflected upon with each respective pilot partner in the Remote Pilot Preparation Workshops. The results of these workshops were listed in the deliverable *D1.1 Multi-actor and knowledge centres co-design and requirements definition report*.

The Pilot Kick-Off Workshop was held in Month 13, September 2023 in Bonn, Germany, to engage the pilot partners in co-creation of the first prototype designs of the user interfaces for the tools to be developed within each pilot. The results of this workshop are summarised in the deliverable *D6.1 Pilot Technical implementation planning, implementation and assessment*.

6.4 IDEATION HACKATHONS

To enhance the exploitation potential of its outcomes, AD4GD engaged in various collaboration activities with its stakeholders by Month 18, leveraging their knowledge and experience to improve the project's outcomes, especially the pilots. Interest was collected early on to understand future potential user requirements from relevant stakeholders.

A face-to-face AD4GD project hackathon was held in Month 14, October 2023 at Aston University, Birmingham, UK. The aim of the hackathon was to start the development of technical components based on a set of requirements identified and refined in online meetings before the hackathon. These components and tools are building blocks of the identified AD4GD KERs. The hackathon was focused on 4 main areas of development: dataspace connectors, connectivity workflow, semantic enrichment, and injection of sensor data into STA/STApplus.

The initial requirements have evolved through subsequent development iterations, and a set of 12 components/component groups needed to support the pilots and the GGDS formed the focus for a second project hackathon, the AD4GD Open Event "European Green Deal Data Space for local air quality decisions" in Month 18, February 2024 in Torino, Italy. More info can be found in the deliverable *D6.1 Pilot Technical implementation planning, implementation and assessment*.

Apart from these, a 3-day hackathon was held in Month 17, January 2024 at the Politecnico di Torino, Italy. The hackathon aimed to integrate the previous developments in the pilots in a consistent way that allows for the AD4GD data space architecture to emerge naturally from a coherent set of building blocks, that were then incorporated as AD4GD KERs.

7 NEXT STEPS

As explained under section 3.1, the T7.4 Exploitation and Sustainability task follows the **Plan, Implement, Validate** strategy. The next 18 months' actions contain the following tasks amongst others:

Plan

- Assist AD4GD partners to elaborate on their individual exploitation plans: The final individual exploitation plans will contain the identification of relevant stakeholders, value proposition, pilot activities for validation, risk analysis, and implementation plan of the identified KER. This will be realised through online workshops, questionnaires, and the partners' individual work.
- Register for the Horizon Results Booster program to develop the final joint exploitation plan up to three main outcomes of the project.

Implement

- KERs will be analysed and prioritised and an exploitation and sustainability strategy will be developed. This should be done in collaboration with the Green Deal Data Space Action Group in EuroGEO.
- Develop three case studies based on learnings from implementing exploitation plans within the pilots.
- Finalise the market scan based on the identified results and develop a business plan for the commercialization strategy.

Validate

- Validate final individual and joint exploitation plans through a co-creation session with the mapped stakeholders.
- Initiate a European Green Deal Data Space cross-disciplinary exploitation workshop with the sister projects: GREAT, B-Cubed, FAIRiCUBE and USAGE.

8 CONCLUSION

The goal of this deliverable *D7.3 GDDS exploitation perspective (initial)* is to provide initial exploitation perspectives both on the partner and on the project level. The deliverable will be a living document and will be continuously updated during the project's lifetime, serving as a reference for the AD4GD project partners. In Month 36, August 2025, this initial plan will be turned into an actionable final exploitation plan, including partners' individual exploitation plans and the AD4GD joint exploitation plan, specifically Deliverable *D7.4 GDDS exploitation perspectives (final)*. This document will summarise the selected Key Exploitable Results (KERs), exploitation mechanisms, and stakeholders interested in sustaining and upscaling the outcomes of the project.

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